

The Research of the Influencing Factors of Chinese Enterprises' Direct Investment in Africa

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Since the founding of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) in 2000, China-Africa economic and trade cooperation has Among them, China's direct investment in Africa has grown rapidly, with \$5.39 billion flowing to Africa in 2018, up 31.5 per cent. Among them, China's direct investment in Africa has grown rapidly, with \$5.39 billion flowing to Africa in 2018, up 31.5% year-on-year, mainly to South Africa, Zambia, Kenya and other countries. Africa has become the fourth largest destination for China's outbound direct investment, In view of Africa's rich resources, vast market and improving investment environment, the influence of Africa on the development of China's OFDI will continue to rise While China's FDI in Africa is increasing, research results on China's FDI in Africa have also been emerging from both domestic These research results not only point out the direction for Chinese enterprises to carry out direct These research results not only point out the direction for Chinese enterprises to carry out direct investment in Africa, but also provide references for government departments to formulate and implement relevant policies.

On the basis of comprehensive theoretical analysis and empirical research, the paper concludes that Chinese enterprises' direct investment in Africa is not only influenced by the market size of host countries, but also by host country resource factors and the empirical results strongly refute the misrepresentations of Western countries about China's predatory investment in African resources. In addition, based on the empirical results, this paper makes recommendations to Chinese enterprises and the Chinese government from an institutional perspective. In addition, based on the empirical results, this paper makes recommendations to Chinese enterprises and the Chinese government from an institutional perspective, i.e., how to emphasize the importance of host country In addition, based on the empirical results, this paper makes recommendations to Chinese enterprises and the Chinese government from an institutional perspective, i.e., how to emphasize the importance of host country in the choice of foreign location, given the established resource factors.

Keywords: OFDI, AFRICA, RESOURCE PERSPECTIVE, INSTITUTIONAL PERSPECTIVE.

Introduction

Since 2013, relying on its strong economic strength and favorable policy environment, China's outbound investment has gradually changed from quantitative accumulation to qualitative improvement, while maintaining a steady growth in investment scale, Chinese enterprises have invested in a wider range of regions, and their investment choices have become more reasonable, and their investment industries have also transitioned from low-end technology-based to high-end technology-based industries. Africa has always been one of the key targets for Chinese enterprises' outward FDI, and the establishment of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation in 2000 has pushed China's FDI in Africa to a higher level, with enterprises taking Africa as a key target for FDI under the guidance of the "going out" strategy. Although the flow of Chinese direct investment in Africa has fluctuated from year to year, the overall trend has been steady and upward. Especially in the current international environment of counter-globalisation, China still achieved a new high level of direct investment in African countries, which indirectly reflects China's full recognition of the economic development of African developing countries. At the 19th National Congress, China proposed for the first time that economic development needs to be transformed into high-quality development, and efficiency is the primary issue that needs to be addressed for high-quality development. This is also reflected in China's outward foreign direct investment, which needs to increase the volume of investment while paying more attention to improving the quality of investment, making full use of various resources and improving the efficiency of investment. Under the inherent requirement of high-quality development, the 2018 Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) clearly stated that China-Africa cooperation needs to focus on the long term and continuously improve the "gold content" of cooperation.

literature review

Market seeking

Market-seeking OFDI refers to OFDI targeting emerging foreign markets, where companies often undertake OFDI activities for reasons such as avoiding trade barriers, broadening and stabilizing markets, and leading entry into markets and trends. Domestic and international research findings agree that the main factor influencing this type of outbound investment is the market size and potential of the destination country. [Buckley et al. \(2007\)](#) analysed Chinese OFDI data from 1984-2001 and concluded through correlation analysis that Chinese OFDI in the late 20th century was significantly and positively correlated with the size of the host market. [Jiang Guanhong \(2012\)](#) uses an investment gravity model to analyse Chinese FDI data in developing countries in Asia and Africa from 2003 to 2009, and investigates the key factors influencing China's location choice when making outward FDI by building a random effects regression, which generally still exhibits market-seeking factors. The results of the empirical analysis also show that Chinese outward FDI has a market-seeking motive. [Dong Yan et al. \(2011\)](#) studied Chinese investment in African countries from 2005 to 2007 and concluded that Chinese investment in African countries mainly depends on factors such as the target country's economy, market and energy reserves. In her study of the factors influencing Chinese direct investment in South

Africa, [Zhang Connie \(2019\)](#) used data from 2001-2015 for her analysis and found that the size of the South African market attracts Chinese firms to make direct investments.

Natural resources

In the current literature on OFDI, natural resources are often considered as one of the important factors, and the acquisition of natural resources in the target country is the main purpose of most OFDI. For example, [Buckley \(2007\)](#) analyses the purpose of Chinese outward investment in detail using empirical data and argues that the search for natural resources is a key factor influencing Chinese outward FDI. [Rodriguez et al. \(2011\)](#) conduct an empirical analysis of the motivations affecting China and find that market size, natural resources and openness to the outside world all have significant effects. [Hao Wenping and Su Jinhong \(2018\)](#) did not find that the resource-seeking aspect had a significant impact on Chinese OFDI, so an analysis from the perspective of natural resources alone may yield one-sided results.

Infrastructure

[Fung and Sun \(2006\)](#), through an extensive analysis of investment data related to destination infrastructure, show that the scale of investment is significantly and positively correlated with local infrastructure, with a focus on roads and railways, and that relatively well-developed infrastructure is usually more attractive to investors. [Chen, Wei-Bing and Wu, Jin \(2019\)](#) used data from 2007-2014 to analyse China's infrastructure to 39 African countries and found a significant positive effect of Chinese infrastructure aid and direct investment in Africa

Institutional influencing factors

Institutional factors are a key component of host country location choice, and institutional theory emphasises the role of formal and informal political, economic and social institutions external to the organisation in shaping attitudes. [Buckley \(2007\)](#) finds that Chinese investment in Africa is relatively high in terms of government involvement and the share of state-owned economies, and tends to invest in countries that have institutional similarities with China. [Xiuru and Li Ronglin \(2015\)](#) using the Heckman model of Chinese investment in 52 African countries between 2003 and 2013 similarly confirms that the institutional environment of the host country plays an important role in Chinese FDI.

Corruption

[Cheung \(2011\)](#) argues that the higher the level of corruption in the host country, the more likely it is to attract Chinese FDI, and concludes that the level of corruption does not influence Chinese FDI in Africa. An econometric analysis of Chinese investment data in 104 host countries from 2003-2006 shows that host countries with higher levels of corruption are more attractive to Chinese investment. Using micro data from the

2005-2012 Chinese Enterprise Directory, [Chen Xiang and Zhou Hao \(2016\)](#) found that corruption would significantly affect the location choice of Chinese firms' OFDI.

Cultural distance

In the OLI paradigm theory, [Dunning \(1993\)](#) mentions that the excessive cultural distance between multinational companies and their host countries has a significant impact on the choice of foreign location. Cultural distance can bring both "outsider disadvantage" and "outsider advantage" to outward FDI. Kang and Jiang (2012) find that countries with greater cultural distance are more attractive to Chinese OFDI through the current status of Chinese FDI in Southeast Asia and East Asia.

Bilateral investment treaty

Bilateral investment treaty (BIT) is a legal agreement between two countries to encourage, protect and promote investment. [Egger and Pfaffemayer \(2004\)](#) conducted an empirical analysis using country-level data for OECD countries and found that BIT in force between countries can increase bilateral investment stock by 30%.

Level of political governance

The impact of the level of political governance on OFDI is often measured by the degree of economic freedom that a country has to produce. [Su Qigang and Zi Shiling \(2018\)](#) used the 2007-2015 direct investment data of Chinese companies in 37 countries in Africa to construct an FGLS model for analysis, and studied the impact of the host country's government governance level and governance distance on overseas investment. Research points out that the level of government governance has a positive effect on direct investment.

Sample and data sources

Based on the principle of data availability and consistency and the changing of the sample , the data consist of total Chinese OFDI stock flow of Chinese companies in 27 African countries and regions during the period 2007-2017 as a sample. The countries selected in this article are: Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Cameroon, Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Egypt, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Libya, Madagascar, a total of 27 countries. The data is mainly obtained from the World Bank, the Ministry of Commerce of China, the statistical bulletin on Chinese OFDI in previous years, the statistical database of China Economic Network and the Global Competitiveness Report.

Dependent variable

This article studies the influencing factors of Chinese companies' direct investment in Africa. In previous studies, most scholars used the flow or stock of direct investment from the home country to the host country as a standard measurement. Therefore, this paper selects China's investment stock data in relevant African countries from 2007 to 2017 as the explained variable.

Independent variables

Market size

The size of the host country's market is one of the key factors affecting OFDI. A review of the literature reveals that many scholars use GDP of domestic production as a measure of market size. Therefore, in this paper, the GDP of the host country in the current year is chosen as a proxy variable.

Natural Resource Endowment

A number of African countries (regions) are rich in natural resources, particularly mineral and oil resources. It is widely believed internationally that the main motivation for Chinese investment in Africa is to access natural resources. As China's economy rises, its need for oil and metal minerals will also increase. In this paper, exports of ores and metals are selected to measure the natural resource variable.

Level of infrastructure

Foreign investment and economic development are mostly dependent on the level of quality of infrastructure, which mainly includes assets such as communications, ports and airports to provide for the needs of the people in society. In this paper, the overall level of infrastructure quality is chosen to measure the level of infrastructure in the host country, with data from the Global Competitiveness Report, where: 1 = very underdeveloped level of quality; 7 = developed level of quality.

Levels of corruption

To measure the level of corruption, the Corruption Control Index, published annually by the World Bank, has been chosen. This index has a range of values from 1 to 6. A value of 1 indicates a low level of corruption and a value of 6 indicates a high level of corruption.

Cultural Distance

Cultural distance refers to the cultural differences possessed by two countries and usually includes factors such as language and religion. This paper uses Kogut and Singh's (1988) Cultural Distance Index (CD) to measure cultural differences, which is calculated using the following formula.

$$CD_i = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{k=1}^6 (I_{ki} - I_k)^2 / V_k$$

where CD_i denotes the cultural difference between China and country i , I_{ki} denotes the score on the k th dimension for country i ; I_k denotes the score on the k th dimension for China, and V_k denotes the variance of the k th dimension scores for all countries.

Bilateral investment treaty

Measured with a 0-1 dummy variable, it indicates whether China has signed a BIT with the host country. Many BIT in the world are signed for a period of time before they become effective, and the content of the clauses before it becomes effective does not play a role. Countries that did not sign a BIT or signed a BIT that did not take effect in the current year are assigned a value of 0. Since the effective year, the value of 1 will be assigned. If the effective of BIT is revised again, it will be regarded as a continuation of the original BIT.

Level of political governance

This paper uses a composite index of economic freedom to measure a country's level of political governance. The Index is one of the most authoritative databases in the world, and evaluates the level of economic freedom in 155 countries and regions, including foreign investment, government intervention in the economy and industry regulation. These indicators are averaged, with lower values indicating freer markets and lower levels of government governance.

Geographical distance

The geographical distance between two countries can have a significant impact on the cost and risk of investment. In accordance with the references this paper takes the distance between two capitals, i.e. the straight line distance between Beijing and the capitals of 27 African countries, with data from the CEPII database.

Openness to foreign investment

Openness to foreign investment reflects the host government's attitude towards foreign investment. This paper uses the share of net FDI inflows attracted by the host country to the GDP of the host country as a measure, with data obtained from the World Bank database.

Bilateral trade

This paper measures bilateral economic and trade relations as a proportion of total trade in goods between the two countries to the combined goods of the host country coefficient variable, data from the Ministry of Commerce website.

Model

$$\text{LNNOFDI}_{ij} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{LNMSIZE}_{ij} + \beta_2 \text{NR} + \beta_3 \text{INFRA}_{ij} + \beta_4 \text{CORUP}_{ij} + \beta_5 \text{CD}_{ij} + \beta_6 \text{BIT}_{ij} + \beta_7 \text{LNEFI}_{ij} + \beta_8 \text{GD}_{ij} + \beta_9 \text{BTR}_{ij} + \beta_{10} \text{OPENES}_{ij}$$

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics

In order to provide a comprehensive picture of the basic characteristics of the sample data and the study

population in this paper, a descriptive analysis of all variables is conducted prior to testing the hypotheses. Descriptive statistics is a set of methods used to generalise and organise data, and can quickly demonstrate the underlying tendencies of the data. In this paper, 27 host countries were used as cross-sectional data and mixed with time to create a sample of 297.

Table:1. Descriptive statistics table for variables

Model variables	Sample size	Minimum value	Maximum value	Average value	Standard deviation
LNOFDI	297	0.81	8.91	5.56	1.64
LNMSIZE	297	5.49	16.19	7.59	1.09
NR	297	0.00	85.97	12.11	18.18
INFRA	297	1.27	3.79	2.45	0.40
CORUP	297	1	4	2.95	0.58
CD	297	2.31	7.67	4.85	1.49
BIT	297	0	1	0.02	0.16
LNEFI	297	3.06	4.34	4.02	0.17
GD	297	7.43	9.47	9.18	0.30
BTRA	297	0	10.77	6.98	1.57
OPENES	297	-6.05	50.63	4.22	6.45

Data source: According to the output results of Stata

Based on the descriptive statistics of the variables in Table 6-1, it can be seen that China's OFDI to the African region over the period 2007-2017 has a minimum value of 0.81 and a maximum value of 8.91, with a standard deviation of 1.64, showing that the actual Chinese OFDI to the African region varies considerably across regions. The same is true for natural resource endowments (NR), which vary considerably from region to region, with a minimum value of 0 and a maximum value of 85.97, with a standard deviation of 18.18, indicating the uneven distribution of resources in different African countries, which may have had an impact on China's OFDI over the period. The negative value of certain countries in the OPENES indicator for that period is likely to be related to the fact that new FDI inflows were smaller than outflows in that period. Among the collated indicators, the standard deviations of the Geographical Distance (GD) and the Logarithm of the Level of Political Governance (LNEFI) categories are small, the former indicating that the overall difference in geographical distance between African countries and China is small, and the latter indicating that the level of government governance varies less in African countries due to their overall relatively underdeveloped regions.

Correlation

Correlation analysis is a statistical method to determine whether variables are interdependent and to analyse the direction and degree of correlation between interdependent variables. In this paper, in order to examine the correlation between the independent and dependent variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to test the significance of the correlation between the two variables, and on this basis, the specific relationship between them was investigated, the results of which are shown in Table 2 .

Table:2 Correlation coefficient matrix for variables

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
OFDI	1										
MSIZE	0.205*	1									
NR	0.131**	-0.193*	1								
INFRA	0.124**	0.149*	-0.028	1							
CORUP	-0.218*	0.165*	-0.038	0.224*	1						
CD	0.381*	0.231*	0.138*	-0.013	0.053	1					
BIT	0.111**	0.115**	-0.089	-0.094***	-0.048	-0.119**	1				
EFI	0.018	0.092	-0.059	0.352*	0.447*	-0.108**	-0.156*	1			
GD	-0.126**	-0.354*	0.218*	0.126**	0.271*	0.081	0.102***	0.170*	1		
OPENES	0.076	0.100***	0.198*	0.014	-0.078	-0.106***	-0.105***	0.019	-0.367	1	
											*
BTRA	0.348*	0.181*	-0.216	0.209*	0.306*	0.243*	0.110**	-0.042	0.073	-0.098***	1
			*								

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01 In the first row of the table, 1, 2, 3.... .13 correspond to the variables on the left.
Data source: According to the output results of Stata

Firstly, we focus on the correlation between the independent and dependent variables. All the independent variables, except economic freedom and openness to foreign investment, show significance to the dependent variable, in line with the expected sign. At the market level, the correlation between market size (MSIZE) and the dependent variable is significant at the 10% level, with a correlation coefficient of 0.205. Both variables at the resource level are significantly correlated with the dependent variable at the 5% level, with correlation coefficients of 0.131 and 0.124, respectively. EFI) were not significant. The control variables Geographical Distance (GD) is negatively and significantly correlated with the dependent variable, Bilateral Economic and Trade Relations (BTRA) is significantly correlated with the dependent variable at the 10% level and Openness to Foreign Investment (OPENES) is insignificant.

Secondly, regarding the correlation between the variables at different levels, the highest correlation coefficient was found between the level of corruption at the institutional level (CORUP) variable and the level of political governance at the institutional level (EFI) variable, at 0.447. It is generally accepted that a correlation coefficient below 0.75 for all variables within the model allows us to make a preliminary judgement that there is no co-linearity between the variables.

Finally, in terms of correlations between variables within each dimension, there is a good degree of independence between variables.

Conclusion

Through the analysis and research in the previous chapters, Chinese enterprises investing in Africa are

influenced not only by market-seeking and resource-seeking, but also by institutional factors in the host country (such as the level of political governance, cultural distance and other factors). Based on a summary of the locational advantage theory, resource perspective and institutional perspective, and taking into account the actual situation of Chinese enterprises' investment in Africa, this paper conducts a theoretical analysis and empirical study on the impact mechanism of Chinese enterprises' direct investment in Africa, and draws the following conclusions.

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